

A combined design-manufacturing-testing investigation of micro- to macro-scale tailoring of open poroelastic materials based on perturbed Kelvin cell micro-geometries.

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Abstract

The properties of open-cell porous materials for acoustic applications are known to be influenced by the micro-structure and micro-geometry of the material, possibly inducing anisotropy in the macroscopic properties of the material. This has obviously repercussions on the modelling of the elasto-acoustic behaviour of such materials. With the rapidly increasing quality and resolution of the additive manufacturing capabilities, some of these questions can now be studied in some more detail and under controlled conditions. The main contributions of this paper are to discuss a jointly pursued complete design-to-test of a Kelvin model based cell micro-structure. From a given micro-structure, the thickness of struts, the aspect ratio of the cell, the stiffness controlled by the joints between struts, etc., the macro-scale properties required for modelling the elasto-acoustic behaviour will be deduced from a combination of numerical simulations and inverse estimation techniques.

1 Introduction

The final objective of the current work is to design an anisotropic homogenised elastic constitutive material model on a macro level. We base our methods on previously published research focussed on anisotropic constitutive material properties and their influence on the vibroacoustic behaviour in different applications, see e.g. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

Our approach is to start from a defined micro-structural geometry that may be parametrised in a systematic and controlled way. We have chosen to work with the well-known Kelvin cell (KC), i.e. the tetrakaidecahedron which is known to fill space completely, see for example the original publication by Lord Kelvin, [10] which was recently reprinted as [11]. Some more recent works on KC mechanics include [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19].

In a dual-scale modelling approach, we build a micro-structural numerical model that is used to predict a certain physical field response, that is then used to extract a homogenised equivalent model through the steps outlined below.

2 From Micro to Macro elasticity modelling

We propose to employ a combined homogenisation-inversion method that takes a well-defined micro-structural geometry as a starting point. We then use the micro-structural model to extract elastic and acoustic properties for a homogenised, equivalent continuum.

For static elasticity this is achieved by computing a series of displacement fields for a given set of static loads and boundary conditions, that are replicated in a homogeneous continuum based elastic model, which is solved using (nominally) the same boundary conditions and loads.

Details on the applied procedures are given in the following. We will first give a general overview of the procedures developed and then get more specific in some cases investigated within the current framework.

2.1 Numerical Kelvin Cell Model

We start from a unit cell template as shown in Figure 1, holding 24 unique struts that may be repeated in x, y, z -directions to form a porous block with known micro-structural geometrical properties. The unit cell dimensions are defined through a set of parameters, i.e. L_x^{cell} , L_y^{cell} and L_z^{cell} of the length, width and height respectively. In addition to these, each of the 24 struts are assigned individual radii, $r_i, i = 1, \dots, 24$. In the investigations performed, we have started our parametrisations from a fixed, nominally isotropic cell with the size H_c , and from this computed the lengths of the individual struts as $L_s = \sqrt{2}H_c/4$. We then introduce a set of scaling parameters that allow us to distort the unit cell, s_x, s_y, s_z , such that e.g. $L_x^{cell} = s_x 4L_s/\sqrt{2}$ etc.

To design a numerical test sample, we then choose the number of cells in each direction as N_x, N_y, N_z , and complement the missing struts at the boundaries, $x = 0$ and $x = N_x L_x^{cell}$; $y = 0$ and $y = N_y L_y^{cell}$; and $z = 0$, as illustrated in Figure 2 for $N_x = N_y = N_z = 15$. For ease of reference, the different faces of the cubic sample are indicated by their outgoing normal in the coordinate system attached to the sample, $x_-, x_+, y_-, y_+, z_-, z_+$. The displacement components are defined as $u = x_0 - x_1, v = y_0 - y_1$ and $w = z_0 - z_1$, where x_0, y_0, z_0 and x_1, y_1, z_1 are the positions of a point in the material before and after loading, respectively. The data used for the approach consists of a set of displacements from the KC model u^{kelvin} . A solid model is constructed to calculate the displacements u^{solid} for a set of elastic moduli, which are varied within an optimisation routine until the difference between measured and predicted displacements is minimised. In the present investigation, the displacements $u^{kelvin} = [u, v, w]$ are obtained as the result of a prescribed static compression d in the z direction. The shear displacement is applied subsequently in x and y directions, and three spatial components of the displacement are extracted at the four free faces of the sample.

Detail boundary and load conditions for inverse estimation during optimization simulations are

- **Boundary conditions:** all movements constrained on the z_+ surface nodes, where $u = v = w = 0$, Fig. 2.
- **Load Step 1:** Compression displacements $w = 0.01$ mm on z_- surface, Fig. 2.
- **Load Step 2:** Shear displacements $u = 0.01$ mm on z_- surface.
- **Load Step 3:** Shear displacements $v = 0.01$ mm on z_- surface.

2.2 Elastic Material Model

Biot [20] described the constitutive laws for porous materials consisting of a solid phase and a fluid phase in acoustic applications. In the case of open-cell porous materials, only the fluid phase takes part in the dynamic deformation. Therefore, the static structural properties of the material, such as elasticity, can conveniently be described in the absence of the fluid phase. Thus, only the solid frame of the material is considered here

and the Hooke's law for the anisotropic material in stiffness form is:

$$\sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{yz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{1111} & D_{1122} & D_{1133} & D_{1112} & D_{1113} & D_{1123} \\ & D_{2222} & D_{2233} & D_{2212} & D_{2213} & D_{2223} \\ & & D_{3333} & D_{3312} & D_{3313} & D_{3323} \\ & & & D_{1212} & D_{1213} & D_{1223} \\ & & & & D_{1313} & D_{1323} \\ & & & & & D_{2323} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{H}_a \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{H}_a is the anisotropic stiffness or Hooke's matrix, $\sigma = [\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{33}, \sigma_{12}, \sigma_{13}, \sigma_{23}]^{-1}$ is the stresses and $\varepsilon = [\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}, \varepsilon_{33}, 2\varepsilon_{12}, 2\varepsilon_{13}, 2\varepsilon_{23}]^{-1} = [\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}, \varepsilon_{33}, \gamma_{12}, \gamma_{13}, \gamma_{23}]^{-1}$ are the strains. If the structure is orthotropic, only 9 parameters are included in the Hooke's stiffness matrix \mathbf{H}_o ,

$$\mathbf{H}_o = \begin{bmatrix} D_{1111} & D_{1122} & D_{1133} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & D_{2222} & D_{2233} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & D_{3333} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & D_{1212} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & D_{1313} & 0 \\ & & & & & D_{2323} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

If the cell structure is isotropic, the linear elastic materials have their elastic properties uniquely determined by any two moduli, e.g. Young's modulus, E , and ν , Poisson's ratio. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio can be calculated according to the relationship between moduli and stiffness parameters in Hooke's matrix, Equation 3.

$$D_{1111} = D_{2222} = D_{3333} = \frac{E(1-\nu)}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}, \quad (3a)$$

$$D_{1122} = D_{1133} = D_{2233} = \frac{E\nu}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}, \quad (3b)$$

$$D_{1212} = D_{1313} = D_{2323} = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}. \quad (3c)$$

2.3 Inverse estimation

The inverse estimation routine is implemented in Matlab using the globally convergent method of moving asymptotes (GCMMA) by [21, 22, 23]. The GCMMA routine pursues a strict decrease of the object function, guaranteeing a set of parameters which is a preferable solution. A detailed description of the GCMMA algorithm is given in the original paper [21]. The criterion to assess whether the optimisation is converged is that a variation in the objective function and in each of the parameters must be less than 10^{-4} between two subsequent iterations.

As has been discussed by Van der Kelen et al [9], the static inversion problem using prescribed displacements is undetermined and one of the moduli has to be estimated in a different numerical experiment. In the present work, prior to the optimization, a separate setup is required to estimate the stiffness component D_{3333} through a numerical compression test where constraints are set for all nodes $u = v = 0$. The estimated $D_{3333} = \sigma_{33}/\varepsilon_{33}$, where $\sigma_{33} = F_{ZminSet}^3/A$, $\varepsilon_{33} = d_3/L_z$, $F_{ZminSet}^3$ is the reaction force in z direction of on z_- nodes, A is the area of the z_- surface, d_3 is the compression displacement on the strain z_- surface, and L_z is the thickness of KC model in z direction. In the inverse estimation procedure, a the material model (moduli) is varied to approximate the measured displacements. In each iteration of the optimisation routine, a homogenised solid model representing the experimental setup is solved for a proposed set of constitutive parameters.

The error between the measured (here from a numerical experiment) and the predicted displacements using the solid model is used as the objective function, defined as the square of the L^2 -norm of the difference between the predicted displacements and the measured displacements, summed over all free faces f , Figure 3, in each loading step s for all points per face,

$$\Pi_{total} = \sum_{s=1}^3 \sum_{f=1}^4 \frac{\| {}^s \mathbf{U}_k^{solid} - {}^s \mathbf{U}_k^{Kelvin} \|^2}{\| {}^s \mathbf{U}_k^{Kelvin} \|^2} \quad (4a)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{solid} = [u, v, w]^{solid} \quad (4b)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{Kelvin} = [u, v, w]^{kelvin} \quad (4c)$$

where \mathbf{U}^{Kelvin} is the target displacements of the average displacements from **Load Steps** s , \mathbf{U}^{solid} is the displacement of the solid model extracted at the same locations as in the KC model by interpolating the nearest point displacement on the solid material surface. Note that the average displacement of the individual KC was obtained from the displacement of its vertex nodes and compare to the solid ones. Thus increasing the KC number would decrease the possible displacement discontinuities from cell to cell and the fixed boundary effects on z_+ surface.

Figure 1: Single Kelvin cell: (a) single cell grouped beam elements based on directions; (b) isotropic cell with same beam elements in all direction; (c) orthotropic cell extended in x direction

To get an understanding of how the differences between simulated and measured displacements are spread, a symbolic representation of the measure of this difference is given for each loading step s ,

$$\Pi_m^s = \sum_{f=1}^4 \frac{\| {}^s \mathbf{U}_k^{solid} - {}^s \mathbf{U}_k^{Kelvin} \|^2}{\| {}^s \mathbf{U}_k^{Kelvin} \|^2} \quad (5)$$

which can be written as a matrix,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_c = [\Pi_u \quad \Pi_v \quad \Pi_w] = \begin{bmatrix} \Pi_{u,1} & \Pi_{v,1} & \Pi_{w,1} \\ \Pi_{u,2} & \Pi_{v,2} & \Pi_{w,2} \\ \Pi_{u,3} & \Pi_{v,3} & \Pi_{w,3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The component $\mu_{u,1}$ for example gives the square of L^2 -norm difference on the displacement components u for **Load Step 1** in the x direction over all four free surfaces, relative to the displacement of the KC model. Note that the subscript c has been introduced in order to identify the results for the different cases tested and discussed in later sections.

2.4 Validation of The Inverse Estimation Approach

There are a number of different possible ways to validate the approach selected here, and we will recapitulate some interesting investigations that we have performed so far. We verified that the inversion would identify

an isotropic KC material, even when the optimization was performed using either an orthotropic constitutive model. Thus, the known material symmetry is not taken into account in the inverse estimation, and each material is addressed as if it were orthotropic.

We also investigated the effects of the number of Kelvin cells used, thus studying the influence of the boundaries; as well as the order of the (linear) beam elements used to model the struts; and finally the required mesh resolution in the solid model, i.e. the number of solid elements used in the simulated displacement computations.

In all the validation cases studied, it is expected that for a symmetric KC geometry, after the displacement error has reached a stable minimum, the estimated Hooke's matrix should have the relationship of Equation 3, where other parameters in the Hooke's matrix are small or close to zero.

We tested different number of cells as well as different beam element types of KC model, in order to investigate the boundary effects and the beam displacement approximation on the final optimization results. In the same way, different number of elements in the mesh of the solid FE model are used to find a reasonable mesh size for optimization.

Equation 7 shows the Hooke's law in compliance form found from the inverse of the compliance matrix in stiffness form Equation 2, where 9 elastic constants in orthotropic constitutive equations are comprised of 3 Young's moduli E_x , E_y , E_z , 3 Poisson's ratios ν_{xy} , ν_{xz} , ν_{xy} , and the 3 shear moduli G_{yz} , G_{zx} , G_{yz} .

$$\mathbf{H}_o = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_x & -\nu_{yx}/E_y & -\nu_{zx}/E_z & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{xy}/E_x & 1/E_y & -\nu_{zy}/E_z & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{xz}/E_x & -\nu_{yz}/E_y & 1/E_z & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{xy} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{xz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{yz} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where $\frac{\nu_{yz}}{E_y} = \frac{\nu_{zy}}{E_z}$, $\frac{\nu_{zx}}{E_z} = \frac{\nu_{xz}}{E_x}$, $\frac{\nu_{xy}}{E_y} = \frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_x}$.

The Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios for the isotropic KC model could be inverse calculated from following four methods with the optimized Hooke's matrix,

- **Method 1:** solve Equations 3(a)–(b);
- **Method 2:** solve Equations 3(a)–(c);
- **Method 3:** solve Equations 3(b)–(c);
- **Method 4:** solve Equations 2 and Equation 7;

The measure of the variation used in order to quantify and validate the proposed method is given by

$$\epsilon_m^E = \frac{|E_{opt,m} - \bar{E}_{opt}|}{\bar{E}_{opt}} \quad (8a)$$

$$\epsilon_m^\nu = \frac{|\nu_{opt,m} - \bar{\nu}_{opt}|}{\bar{\nu}_{opt}} \quad (8b)$$

where \bar{E}_{opt} is the mean value of the Young's moduli $E_{opt,m}$ best fit of the model, resulting from the inverse estimation of **Method** m above.

Figure 2: Boundary constraint on the surface nodes with maximal z surface z_+ and compression displacements on the minimal z surface z_- .

3 Validation of Inverse Estimation Method Results

3.1 Isotropic KC Models with Different Size

Three sizes ($15 \times 15 \times 15$, $30 \times 30 \times 30$ and $40 \times 40 \times 40$) of a symmetric (and thus expected to be isotropic) KC model were used to verify the inverse estimation method and find an economical and efficient size for both the experimental and the simulation model. Linear and quadratic beam elements were used for the struts (ligaments) of the KC models. As an example of the observations made, Figure 4 shows that the stiffness of D_{3333} decreases as the number of cells are increased in each direction or when using quadratic beam elements (B32) instead of linear elements (B31). This indicates that the stiffening effects of the boundaries are reduced (the KC model becomes softer) as the number of cells are increasing or when quadratic beam elements, but the influence on the estimated moduli is small ($< 3\%$).

In the solid FE model, 3D quadratic reduced Hex (hexahedral) mesh (C3D20R) elements. For the symmetric (isotropic) KC model, seven cases were addressed to verify the estimation method and find a proper balance between accuracy and computationa cost in modelling the structure,

1. Case 1: $15 \times 15 \times 15$ cell isotropic KC model with linear beam elements and $20 \times 20 \times 20$ Hex solid model, named '15Kelvin20Hex';
2. Case 2: $15 \times 15 \times 15$ cell isotropic KC model with quadratic beam elements and $20 \times 20 \times 20$ Hex orthotropic solid model, named as '15QKelvin20Hex';
3. Case 3: $30 \times 30 \times 30$ cell isotropic KC model with linear beam elements and $30 \times 30 \times 30$ Hex orthotropic solid model, named as '30Kelvin30Hex';

Figure 3: Inverse estimation flowchart.

4. Case 4: 30 × 30 × 30 cell isotropic KC model with quadratic beam elements and 30 × 30 × 30 Hex orthotropic solid model, named ‘30QKelvin30Hex’;
5. Case 5: 40 × 40 × 40 cell isotropic KC model with linear beam elements and 40 × 40 × 40 Hex orthotropic solid model, named ‘40Kelvin40Hex’;
6. Case 6: 30 × 30 × 30 cell isotropic KC model with quadratic beam elements and 30 × 30 × 30 Hex anisotropic solid model, named ‘30QKelvin40HexAniso’;
7. Case 7: 30 × 30 × 30 cell isotropic KC model with quadratic beam elements and 40 × 40 × 40 Hex orthotropic solid model, named ‘30QKelvin40Hex’.

As an alternative, for the isotropic KC model, an initial Poisson’s ratio could have been estimated through a compression test instead of using a random value to improve the convergence, by comparing the deformation in x and y directions with a displacement loading in the z direction, where the KC model has a constraint $w = 0$ on the z_+ surface and a compression displacement $w = 0.01\text{mm}$ on the z_- surface. A good starting point for the Hooke’s matrix was given from Equation 3 with the estimated Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.3786$ and D_{3333} in Figure 4. Note that the starting point for the optimisation can be chosen arbitrarily and the final solution does not depend on the chosen starting point.

Figure 5 shows the iteration history of the convergence error as the objective function in Cases 1–7 with the same starting Hooke’s matrix. Cases 1–4 show the objective function does not change much even when quadratic beam elements (B32) were used instead of linear beam elements for KC model. Case 5 and Case 7 show increasing numbers of Kelvin cells could decrease the convergence error, which decreases the boundary effects. Case 4 and Case 7 show increasing mesh numbers of the solid model from 30 × 30 × 30 to 40 × 40 × 40 for the 30 × 30 × 30 quadratic KC model could decrease the convergence error. Case 6 and Case 7 show that using an anisotropic solid model to simulate the isotropic KC model could also decrease the convergence error by over-fitting the boundary effects with 21 non-zero parameters of a full anisotropic matrix.

Figure 4: Estimated stiffness D_{3333} variation as the number of cells of KC model with linear and non-linear beam elements are varied.

Figure 5: Iteration history of objective function for isotropic KC model.

Since the solid model needs to be solved many times before finding a convergent result, the computational time should be traded against the error in the cost function. Much larger computation times are required if we increase the solid meshes, e.g., from Case 4 and Case 7. Thus models of $30 \times 30 \times 30$ Hex and KC were suggested with a good convergence behaviour, final estimated moduli and acceptable computational time. A more accurate result could be obtained by using finer meshes with a starting point found from a coarse mesh, e.g., using the optimized Hooke's matrix of Case 1 as a starting point in Case 5.

Figure 6 shows the average Young's modulus ($E_{avg} = (E_x + E_y + E_z)/3$) and Poisson's ratio ($\nu_{avg} = \nu_x + \nu_y + \nu_z$) in Case 1, Case 3 and Case 5 estimated from **Methods 1–4**. **Method 1** and **Method 4** give very close results. As the cell numbers increased from 15 to 30 in each direction, the variation of the averaged Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the four methods decreased. The average Young's modulus of **Method 1–4** is 10.7MPa, 10.5MPa and 10.6MPa and the average Poisson's ratio is 0.378, 0.380 and 0.379 for Cases 1, 3 and 5, which are very close, within 2% of the average Young's modulus and 0.6% of the average Poisson's ratio.

Figure 7 shows the estimated stiffness and the convergence errors of the $30 \times 30 \times 30$ Kc quadratic beam model compared to the $10 \times 10 \times 10$, $20 \times 20 \times 20$, $30 \times 30 \times 30$, $40 \times 40 \times 40$ Hex solid models respectively. The same starting Hooke's matrix was given as for the other cases in this section. After 4 iterations, a stable convergence error was reached for all cases. Figures 7 (a)–(c) show that the case of $30 \times 30 \times 30$ Hex solid model gives a minimal variation of stiffness. The variation of coupling stiffness [D_{1122} , D_{1113} , D_{2233}] and shear stiffness [D_{1212} , D_{1313} , D_{2323}] decreases as the number of Hex increasing from $10 \times 10 \times 10$ to $30 \times 30 \times 30$. However, if the number of Hex increases to $40 \times 40 \times 40$, the variation increases a little since a finer solid model catches the boundary effects, but the convergence error decreases to less than 1%.

Table 1 shows the estimated engineering constants for the isotropic KC model in Cases 1–7 from **Method 4**. All cases give a modulus in each direction which is close but there exist small acceptable deviations, e.g., Young's moduli deviate $< 1\%$ in Case 6 from mean value of Cases 1–7. The solid orthotropic model with finer meshes, Case 7, gives the lowest deviations for Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios and shear moduli. One main reason is that a finer mesh solid structure is more close to the KC model since a single KC has more free points (24 for linear beam KC) than a Hex (20 point for C3D20R Hex). A solid model with coarse meshes would be stiffer than a KC model, which could be equivalent to a applied stiffer boundary constrain and generate a stiffer Young's modulus in the z -direction, Table 1.

Table 1: Engineering constants for the isotropic KC model

Eng.const	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	mean
E_x [MPa]	10.84	10.68	10.75	10.43	10.77	10.73	10.51	10.67
E_y [MPa]	10.84	10.65	10.75	10.43	10.77	10.73	10.51	10.67
E_z [MPa]	12.01	11.1	11.37	10.30	11.13	11.13	10.31	11.05
ν_{xy} [-]	0.447	0.405	0.416	0.365	0.401	0.403	0.361	0.400
ν_{yx} [-]	0.447	0.404	0.416	0.365	0.401	0.403	0.361	0.400
ν_{xz} [-]	0.317	0.352	0.344	0.390	0.357	0.356	0.392	0.359
ν_{zx} [-]	0.351	0.366	0.364	0.385	0.369	0.369	0.384	0.358
ν_{yz} [-]	0.318	0.354	0.344	0.390	0.357	0.356	0.392	0.359
ν_{zy} [-]	0.352	0.369	0.364	0.385	0.369	0.369	0.384	0.370
G_{xy} [MPa]	3.85	3.77	3.81	3.77	3.81	3.80	3.72	3.79
G_{xz} [MPa]	3.66	3.62	3.78	3.57	3.77	3.79	3.56	3.68
G_{yz} [MPa]	3.64	3.61	3.78	3.57	3.77	3.78	3.56	3.67

3.2 Robustness of the Method

The robustness of the proposed characterisation method was studied for the isotropic KC model. The uncertainties in the experiment were studied, e.g., 5% of the measurement error of the loading displacement,

Figure 6: The average Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for linear beam KC model by inverse estimated methods with data from optimization results, Section 2.4.

Figure 7: The estimated stiffness and convergent error for $30 \times 30 \times 30$ isotropic KC model respectively to different number of Hex in the solid model.

or 5% of the measurement error of the sample dimensions. The difference in the engineering constants is smaller than the uncertainty on the sample dimensions.

In the cases where an isotropic constitutive model was fitted using an orthotropic, the optimization tends to compensate for the error related to the boundary effects, when fewer elements were used in the solid model than the number of cells in the KC model. For example, Figure 8 shows the shear modulus D_{1212} decreased from a convergence point (iteration 4) after 15 more iterations where Π_{total} decreased less than 10^{-4} but one component, Π_w , increased more than the decreased Π_{total} . Thus an over-fitting of the shear modulus G_{xy} might happen if a stiffer solid model was used after the convergence criterion was reached. In order to avoid this, the optimized Hooke's matrix could be checked if any of the error components ($\Pi_i, U = u, v, \text{ or } w$) increased when the total error decreased when the convergent error decreased less than 10^{-4} after several iterations. One way to increase the robustness of the optimization is to use a starting point from a coarsely meshed optimization in a finely meshed solid model. Then only a few steps are required to capture a more accurate result for the shear modulus.

4 Orthotropic Kelvin Foam

The proposed method was subsequently applied to an orthotropic KC model, which is obtained by stretching the Kelvin cells in the x direction twice ($s_x = 2 \times s_y = 2 \times s_z$) but keeping the cell height H_z as before, Figure 1 (c). Here a KC model using $30 \times 30 \times 30$ and the same number of Hex elements were used. A starting point for the inverse estimation was taken from the isotropic Case 3 in Table 1. Table 2 shows the optimized results of convergence error, stiffness, Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios of the orthotropic Kelvin foam. The total convergence error is 2.34% and the v displacement has the smallest error compared to that of u and w . After applying the inverse estimation method, the cost function found a minimum and an equivalent Hooke's matrix was found. Comparing the obtained Young's moduli with mean data of the isotropic KC models in Table 1, E_x increased 76.3%, and E_y, E_z decreased 87.2% and 84.8% respectively.

Figure 8: The iteration history of the cost function and the estimated stiffness of Case 5: (40Kelvin40Hex). (a), the cost function error and its contributions from components related to displacements u , v and w ; (b), the estimated stiffness; (c), cost function and its components normalised to their initial iteration error; (d), the estimated stiffness components normalised to their initial iteration one.

5 Discussion of the Inverse Estimation Method

The proposed characterisation method is verified for symmetric Kelvin cell models, using different number of cells and shape function order in the beam elements in the experimental models and different number of elements in the solid models. For all cases, the objective function decreases monotonically as is expected for the optimisation algorithm used. For the isotropic KC model, the difference between different settings of the engineering constants is small and a finer meshed model gives a lower convergence error and deviations between moduli and Poisson's ratios in each direction. If a good start point was given from a coarse mesh or compression tests, the inverse estimation converged within a relatively small number of iterations. Note that, although the material is isotropic, the optimal Hooke's tensor deviates slightly from isotropy, as a result shear moduli D_{1212} , D_{1313} and D_{2323} are not converged to exactly the same value, and perfect isotropy is not reached. If the inverse estimation had been allowed similar freedoms (flexibility) in both solid and KC models, full convergence and perfect isotropy would have been reached. But even using coarse meshes for the solid model, the basic characteristics including shear moduli are found. The relative square of L^2 -norm difference in displacement between KC and solid with finer meshes, Case 7, is smaller than 0.8% for all four surfaces, and is smallest for the longitudinal displacement components, Π_w .

The verified inverse estimation method was extended to the application of orthotropic models. The target displacements are obtained with very good accuracy for all components. These numerical examples confirm that the computational part of the inverse estimation works accurately, for structures from isotropic to fully anisotropic.

Figure 9: The displacements computed for a Kelvin cell model and for a solid FE model.

Table 2: Engineering constants for the orthotropic KC model

Quantity	Value	Unit
square of L^2 -norm displacement error, Π	2.34	%
components of Π , $[\Pi_u, \Pi_v, \Pi_w]$	[0.78 1.08 0.49]	%
Stiffness parameters $[D_{1111}, D_{2222}, D_{3333}]$	[42.35, 3.38, 4.44]	MPa
Stiffness parameters $[D_{1122}, D_{1133}, D_{2212}]$	[7.68, 8.82, 1.89]	MPa
Stiffness parameters $[D_{1212}, D_{1313}, D_{2323}]$	[1.66, 2.13, 0.91]	MPa
Young's moduli, $[E_x, E_y, E_z]$	[18.82, 1.95, 2.57]	MPa
Poisson's ratios, $[\nu_{xy}, \nu_{xz}; \nu_{yx}, \nu_{yz}; \nu_{zx}, \nu_{zy}]$	[1.53, 1.34; 0.16, 0.11; 0.18, 0.14]	-

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